

Report 150715

Overview	Name	[overload 150715] road-runner
	Description	road-runner
	Status	FINISHED
	Identity	ff6yb5qbao6hnvi346ix
	Creation date	2025-02-11 16:53:42.660+00:00
	Start date	2019-01-04 15:59:32.262+00:00
	End date	2019-01-04 16:09:36.480+00:00
	Target	185.147.80.168:None
	Configuration	ff6cscxdysjraecaqs72

Case: overall

Density distribution of response times

Response time quantiles

	q50
	q75
	q80
	q85

Network response codes

HTTP response codes

Instances

Monitoring

Host ab61b3d4e7e718c27957cd5e6978f324

Memory

Net

System

cpu-cpu-total

diskio-vda1

diskio-vda2

net-eth0

netstat

Tables

Response time quantiles

Test	Case
ff6yb5qbao6hnvi346ix	overall

Network response codes

Test	Case	0
ff6yb5qbao6hnvi346ix	overall	285030

HTTP response codes

Test	Case	200
ff6yb5qbao6hnvi346ix	overall	285030

Configurations

ff6cscxdysjraecaqs72

```

android:
  enabled: false
  package: yandextank.plugins.Android
autostop:
  autostop: []
  enabled: true
  package: yandextank.plugins.Autostop
  report_file: autostop_report.txt
bfg:
  enabled: false
  package: yandextank.plugins.Bfg
console:
  cases_max_spark: 120
  cases_sort_by: count
  disable_all_colors: false
  disable_colors: ''
  enabled: true
  info_panel_width: 33
  max_case_len: 32
  package: yandextank.plugins.Console
  short_only: false
  sizes_max_spark: 120
  times_max_spark: 120
core:
  affinity: ''
  artifacts_base_dir: ./logs
  artifacts_dir: null
  cmdline: /usr/local/bin/yandex-tank
  lock_dir: /var/lock/
  message: ''
  pid: 1
  taskset_path: taskset
  uuid: 5172c208-7ff9-4ea7-8554-7db4bbbbfc27
influx:

```

```
enabled: false
package: yandextank.plugins.Influx
jmeter:
  enabled: false
  package: JMeter
json_report:
  enabled: true
  monitoring_log: monitoring.log
  package: yandextank.plugins.JsonReport
  test_data_log: test_data.log
overload:
  api_address: https://overload.yandex.net/
  api_attempts: 60
  api_timeout: 10
  chunk_size: 500000
  component: ''
  connection_timeout: 30
  enabled: true
  ignore_target_lock: false
  job_dsc: road-runner
  job_name: road-runner
  jobno_file: jobno_file.txt
  lock_targets: auto
  log_data_requests: false
  log_monitoring_requests: false
  log_other_requests: false
  log_status_requests: false
  maintenance_attempts: 10
  maintenance_timeout: 60
  meta:
    ammo_path: '/var/loadtest/ '
    cmdline: /usr/local/bin/yandex-tank
    jobno: 150715
    loop_count: 285029
    target_host: 185.147.80.168
    target_port: 8000
  network_attempts: 60
  network_timeout: 10
  notify: []
  operator: null
  package: yandextank.plugins.DataUploader
  send_status_period: 10
  strict_lock: false
  target_lock_duration: 30m
  task: ''
  threads_timeout: 60
  token_file: overload_token.txt
  ver: ''
  writer_endpoint: ''
phantom:
  additional_libs: []
  address: 185.147.80.168:8000
  affinity: ''
  ammo_limit: -1
  ammo_type: phantom
  ammofile: ''
  autocasess: 0
  buffered_seconds: 2
  cache_dir: null
  chosen_cases: ''
  client_certificate: ''
  client_cipher_suites: ''
  client_key: ''
  config: ''
  connection_test: true
  enabled: true
```

```
enum_ammo: false
file_cache: 8192
force_stepping: 0
gatling_ip: ''
header_http: '1.0'
headers: []
instances: 1000
load_profile:
  load_type: rps
  schedule: line(1, 500, 60s) const(500, 540s)
loop: -1
method_options: ''
method_prefix: method_stream
multi: []
package: yandextank.plugins.Phantom
phantom_http_entity: 8M
phantom_http_field: 8K
phantom_http_field_num: 128
phantom_http_line: 1K
phantom_modules_path: /usr/lib/phantom
phantom_path: phantom
phout_file: ''
port: ''
source_log_prefix: ''
ssl: false
tank_type: http
threads: null
timeout: 11s
uris:
- /
use_caching: true
writelog: all
rcassert:
  enabled: true
  fail_code: 10
  package: yandextank.plugins.RCAssert
  pass: ''
rcheck:
  disk_limit: 2048
  enabled: true
  interval: 10s
  mem_limit: 512
  package: yandextank.plugins.ResourceCheck
shellexec:
  catch_out: false
  enabled: true
  end: ''
  package: yandextank.plugins.ShellExec
  poll: ''
  post_process: ''
  prepare: ''
  start: ''
telegraf:
  config: monitoring.xml
  config_contents: "<Monitoring>\n <Host address=\"185.147.80.168\" interval=\"1\" \
  \ username=\"ansible\">\n   <CPU/> <Kernel/> <Net/> <System/> <Memory/> <Disk/>\
  \ <Netstat /> <Nstat/>\n </Host>\n</Monitoring>\n"
  default_target: localhost
  disguise_hostnames: true
  enabled: true
  kill_old: false
  package: yandextank.plugins.Telegraf
  ssh_timeout: 30s
```